

REFERENCES

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ERRATUM

Equation (4.28) in I (my previous paper [4]) contains an error. It should read

$$\varepsilon''(0) = - \frac{8\pi G \varepsilon(R)\varepsilon(0)}{3c^4 [1+B I(0)]}$$

$$= - \frac{8\pi G}{3c^4} \varepsilon(0) [\varepsilon(0) + p(0)] < 0$$

(4.28) in I